

The Politics of Wildfires: A Review and Research Agenda

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Abstract

This review synthesizes political and social science research on wildfire politics focused on the Global South, offering a multi-scalar framework encompassing four proposed levels of analysis: supra-politics, state-politics, para-politics, and infra-politics. Challenging dominant technocratic and Global North-centric paradigms, the article emphasizes how power, knowledge systems, and socio-economic practices, alongside international and national norms and institutions, shape fire regimes and management strategies. The analysis highlights the complexity of wildfire politics by examining how fires are governed, contested, and symbolically charged across diverse landscapes and socio-political contexts. Following the review of 147 peer-reviewed articles published between 2000 and 2024, the article calls for a multidisciplinary, decolonial, and context-sensitive approach to fire governance. We ultimately argue that wildfire politics cannot be fully understood without recognizing the socio-ecological interdependencies and political dynamics that structure land use, livelihoods, and environmental justice in fire-prone regions.

Keywords: wildfire politics; wildfire governance; fire management; political ecology of fire; climate action; decolonise wildfire narratives; environmental justice; Global South.

Introduction

Fire acts as a key socio-ecological interface between nature and society (Smith 2021), playing a primary role in shaping livelihoods and transforming ecosystems (Bowman et al. 2011; Moura et al. 2019; Humphrey et al. 2021). Human societies influence fire regimes by altering ignition patterns, modifying fuel loads, suppressing fires, and emitting greenhouse gases (Archibald 2016; McLauchlan et al. 2020). In the pyric transition to modernity, anthropogenic fires have increasingly replaced natural fire patterns (Pyne 2009). Global warming – essentially a crisis of combustion (Pyne 2001), has triggered a new era of anthropogenic burning (Kelly et al. 2020), reshaping fire patterns and leading to more destructive and severe wildfires worldwide. Despite this, fire ecology remains poorly understood within policy discussions and is insufficiently incorporated into institutional frameworks. Decades of aggressive fire suppression policies, while intended to mitigate wildfire risks, have instead exacerbated them by increasing fuel accumulation and weakening traditional management practices (Busenberg 2004; Jensen 2006; Gillson et al. 2019; Moura et al. 2019; Duane et al. 2021). This *wildfire*

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paradox (Tendim et al. 2021) is further compounded by deeply rooted perceptions that regard fire as a threat, a viewpoint that has often intensified tensions between state authorities and fire-dependent communities (Eloy et al. 2018).

The emphasis on fire suppression is driven by a widespread belief in rising fire activity, fuelled by skewed reporting on ignition causes that ignore the conditions of flammable landscapes (such as fuel buildup) and sensationalist media coverage of extreme events (Harrison et al. 2021). From the Amazon rainforest to the Australian bushland, recent attention to “megafires” has been fuelled by emotionally charged narratives and distressing imagery, sparking global outrage and protest. Although fire seasons have been lengthening in many regions (McLauchlan et al. 2020), current data do not support the notion of an overall increase in fire activity. In fact, this perception contradicts evidence showing a decline in both the total area burned and the number of fires over the past thirty years (Doerr & Santín 2016; Andela et al., 2017). Most critically, mainstream discussions on the topic overlook the fact that fire is a “necessary perturbation” for ecosystem preservation and regeneration (Doerr & Santín 2016) and fails to distinguish between fire-free and fire-prone ecosystems (Kelly et al. 2020; Harrison et al. 2021). Wildfire misinformation stems from oversimplifying the complex causes and consequences of wildfires, leading to broad generalisations that obscure ecosystem-specific variations and misconceptions about effective management practices (Jones et al. 2022). For instance, suppression-focused strategies miss another paradox in modern fire management: the imbalance of fire types, whereby, simply put, “the developed world has too few good burns and the developing world too many bad ones” (Pyne 2009: 4).

Critical disaster studies highlight that framing wildfires as catastrophic events requiring intervention introduces coverage, normative, temporal, and spatial biases (Balaban & Fu 2014; Doerr & Santín 2016; Croker et al. 2024). Beyond distorting public understanding, the focus on suppression also has significant implications for fire governance. By treating fires solely as crises requiring immediate control rather than as ecological processes, this perspective reinforces reactive policy approaches that may be misguided or even harmful (Silva et al. 2019). In fact, it can promote technocratic forms of environmental governance, leading to the dispossession and marginalisation of local communities (Cary 2023). The narrow framing of wildfires as natural disasters risks reproducing (neo)colonial views and practices that overlook diverse relationships between fire and societies. As a result, a “rational debate about options for coexisting with inherently flammable landscapes” is undermined (Bowman et al. 2011: 6).

We agree that the public debate would benefit from a shift towards a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing both large-scale and local variations in fire activity, including their interconnections and interdependencies (Schwartz et al. 2015). To deepen our understanding of wildfires, it is crucial to place human agency at the heart of fire ecology, recognizing that fire-related challenges are integral to coupled socio-ecological systems (Moritz et al. 2014). Moreover, it is essential to broaden the scope and depth of scholarship in this field. Social science research has predominantly approached fire management and regulation from a problem-solving perspective, with a strong focus on the Global North (McCaffrey et al. 2012). This research trajectory has explored key areas such as fire mitigation and management practices, community preparedness, public response, citizen–agency communication, and post-fire recovery (Davis 2001; Busenberg 2004; O’Laughlin 2005; Dale 2006; Jensen 2006; Steelman & Burke 2007; Moritz et al. 2014). However, this technical scope

and limited geographic lens overlook the broader political dimensions surrounding fire, particularly in the Global South.

In recent years, the proliferation of review articles on the governance of wildfires (da Veiga & Nikolakis 2022; Sousa et al. 2022; Vazquez et al. 2022; Crocker et al. 2023; Kirschner et al. 2023; Huidobro et al. 2024) demonstrates both the growing interest within the scientific community and some pressing unresolved questions in the field. Despite efforts to standardise terminology, significant differences remain in the scientific literature when describing fire types, with terms reflecting varying disciplinary, regional, and contextual nuances often used interchangeably (Huidobro et al. 2024). This linguistic uncertainty also causes confusion at the policy level. In light of a rapidly evolving field marked by emerging findings and perspectives, this article seeks to synthesise and conceptualise the current state of knowledge on wildfire politics in the Global South. It challenges the dominant technocratic narratives, frequently shaped by Global North perspectives, by highlighting the colonial legacy embedded in mainstream fire management approaches. By offering a comprehensive theoretical framework that incorporates local knowledge and power structures, this review article aims to foster a layered understanding of fire dynamics and provide a foundation for comparing context-specific studies.

We propose the notion of wildfire politics as the study of how power, governance, and knowledge systems interact in determining fire management and regulation in rural landscapes³. While acknowledging that fire activity is predominantly anthropogenic, we retain the often-abused prefix *wild* to emphasize the influence of media narratives and power dynamics in shaping policy responses that may oversimplify or misrepresent the true nature of fire activity. Thus, the concept reflects a persistent tension between ecological fire regimes and technocratic policies that are disconnected from local ecologies. By placing politics at the forefront, the aim of this paper is to re-politicise fire research. Particularly in rural settings, where traditional land management practices and livelihoods depend on its controlled use, fire is a deeply embedded socio-political issue. This review seeks to bridge gaps in the literature by examining the intersections between wildfires, rural livelihoods, and development pathways across the Global South, where these linkages are most pronounced. It also offers a novel theoretical framework that illuminates the many political drivers behind fire regimes and practices.

Unpacking the Politics of Wildfires

We live in a world where fire is an ever-present force, whether controlled or wild. As “creatures of fire” who coexist with it (Ulloa & Barton 2024), we recognize fire as both a practical tool and a powerful symbol in society. Just as a chemical reaction requires specific conditions to ignite and sustain, the presence and impact of fire are shaped by the power dynamics that drive material accumulation and create incendiary landscapes (Goldstein 2019). However, the tendency in policy and academic discourse to focus on individual blame for fire-setting often obscures the structural factors that make landscapes fire-prone in the first place, much like how climate change discussions frequently depoliticize the “causal connections between landscape fires and the actors ultimately responsible

³ In this article, we refer to fires occurring in rural or semi-rural areas, typically involving grasslands, agricultural lands, forests, or other undeveloped landscapes.

not for igniting fires but for creating the conditions that enable them” (ivi: 7). Although existing literature has examined various drivers and motivations (Schwartz et al. 2015; Carmenta et al. 2017; Cammelli et al. 2020; Duane et al. 2021), the deeper dynamics are rarely analysed in a comparative manner. Fire management requires balancing competing interests and values; these trade-offs cannot be addressed solely through technical interventions (Smith 2021). A political ecology perspective is thus essential for enriching our incomplete understanding of how fire occurs, is regulated, and perceived across diverse contexts (Eriksen 2007). This review article proposes a theory-driven framework for analysing wildfires as political phenomena. We argue that wildfire patterns cannot be fully understood, let alone effectively managed, without considering the broader political drivers that underpin them.

This relationship is evident across the Global South, where wildfires are frequently closely tied to subsistence and land tenure, and therefore to issues of inequality and social justice. Although “Global North” and “Global South” can oversimplify the diverse realities within regions, they still offer valuable insights for differentiating wildfire patterns. This distinction highlights the stark contrast between Earth’s two major combustion realms – one relying on fossil fuels and the other on surface biomass – as vividly depicted in nighttime satellite imagery (Pyne 2009). In the Global North, the increase in fire-affected areas is largely driven by the expansion of the wildland–urban interface. These fires are often ignited accidentally and can become uncontrollable due to the accumulation of fuel in fire-prone environments that have not burned regularly because of fire suppression efforts (Moreno et al. 1998; Pausas & Vallejo 1999; Pausas et al. 2008; Scott 2018). In contrast, in the Global South, the intentional setting of fires linked to livelihood practices (e.g., slash and burn, honey harvesting, hunting, pasture regeneration) plays a crucial role in shaping fire regimes. These practices are part of customary land management aimed at increasing forage for livestock and wildlife or clearing land for agriculture where mechanisation is limited. Additionally, particularly in authoritarian contexts or where democratic participation is limited, burning becomes a common tactic for social contention to assert land claims or protest state policies. Although these practices can sometimes lead to extreme fire events (Alencar et al. 2015; Schwartz et al. 2015), they are generally motivated by political or economic development strategies. Finally, the commodification of wildfires as part of agribusiness expansion is common in low- and middle-income countries, often facilitated by entrenched collusion and corruption among political and economic elites (Varkkey 2013; Cano-Crespo et al. 2015; Cammelli et al. 2020).

A key takeaway from the literature reviewed for this article is that both the benefits and costs of burning manifest at various scales and accrue to different actors, depending on the political, economic, and social dynamics. To capture these processes, we introduce a framework that distinguishes between four interrelated layers, each contributing to the shaping of fire landscapes in relation to different scales: i) supra-politics; ii) state-politics; iii) para-politics; and iv) infra-politics. These layers can be visualised as concentric circles, reflecting different scales from macro to micro. The influence of these layers on fire regimes can vary significantly, and in the real world, messy interconnections across scales are the norm, rather than discrete ideal types. For instance, peatland fires in Indonesia exemplify the interplay between patrimonial elites colluding with foreign corporations and local survival strategies amid weak state enforcement, all set against the backdrop of regional cooperation to mitigate transboundary haze. We begin here from an analysis of each scale and what the literature tells us about it, hoping that this linear approach will contribute to bridge

knowledge gaps and clarifying the connections between wildfires and various political dynamics. Notably, this theoretical framework broadens our understanding of politics by expanding the scope of actors and processes beyond traditional state-centred approaches. Although fire management and regulation are typically the responsibilities of state agencies and departments, wildfire patterns encompass multiple levels of society and governance.

Just as fire acts as an interface between humans and nature, it also serves as a cross-disciplinary interface. However, despite calls for interdisciplinary research, a significant divide persists between the social and natural sciences, with the latter often dominating (Carmenta et al. 2011; Croker et al. 2023). Efforts like pyro-geography (O'Connor et al. 2011; Bowman et al. 2013) have aimed to integrate these fields, but fire is not generally viewed as a unifying theme (Pyne 2009), resulting in siloed approaches and a disconnect between policy, science, and lived experiences (Devisscher et al. 2018). Practical and epistemological challenges make true interdisciplinarity difficult (Goldstein et al. 2020). For instance, quantitative studies that include socioeconomic variables often fail to examine these factors in depth, leading to superficial explanatory models that pass over the complexities of human interactions and historical contexts (Sousa et al. 2022). Conversely, fine-grained studies on informal political dynamics, such as those investigating patronage or corruption, are often limited to single case studies, lacking broader applicability. This integrative literature review article (Torraco 2005) addresses the aforementioned issues by promoting an interdisciplinary and intercultural dialogue informed by recent research in political ecology, environmental economics, and human geography, with the goal of establishing a foundation for a new research agenda.

The literature search was conducted between April and August 2024 by retrieving peer-reviewed articles published in English from 2002 onward through EBSCOhost. We used the following search string: *("politics" OR "drivers" OR "policy" OR "management") AND ("fire*" OR "burn*" OR "wildfire*") AND ("Africa" OR "Asia" OR "South America" OR "Central America" OR "Global South")*. The timeframe was selected to correspond with the period during which high-quality remote sensing fire data have become available. This has driven the growth of a body of literature in ecology and environmental sciences on fire. Our focus, however, is on examining how the literature on social and political sciences related to this topic has developed over this period. Therefore, we concentrate on studies that illuminate the contested nature of fire governance, excluding those that focused on climatic and vegetation models without addressing sociopolitical factors. Furthermore, we leave out studies that relied exclusively on satellite remote sensing data for fire modelling unless they incorporated supplementary data collection methods. This decision stems from the understanding that, while daily satellite observations and global coverage have significantly advanced fire ecology by providing new insights into burning patterns and mapping of burned areas (McLauchlan et al. 2020), exclusive reliance on geospatial technologies has notable drawbacks. In addition to limitations in accurately representing specific fires at small scales (Goldstein 2019), these technologies can diminish the value of ground-level analyses of landscape burning in favour of technocratic representations that shun situated indigenous knowledge and local practices (Sletto 2008; Eriksen & Hankins 2014; Mistry et al. 2016; Eloy et al. 2018, 2019; Cary 2023). To maintain geographic focus, research from the Global North, including studies on indigenous fire management in Australia and Canada, was excluded. Grey literature was also omitted to ensure methodological consistency and rigour.

Using the EBSCOhost research platform, an initial pool of 3,427 articles was identified. To ensure relevance and rigor, each abstract was carefully reviewed and screened against predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. This process resulted in the selection of 147 articles deemed pertinent to the topic. For the analysis phase, an open coding approach was employed to facilitate data extraction. This method enabled the identification of recurring patterns across the selected literature. A total of 56 initial codes emerged from this inductive process. These codes were then systematically organized into eight descriptive categories to streamline the analysis. This procedure followed a similar approach to that used by Vazquez et al. (2022), who emphasized iterative reading and thematic clustering to derive conceptual insights from complex bodies of literature. Although our aim is to provide a comprehensive and up-to-date overview of the scientific knowledge on the politics of wildfires across the Global South, we are aware that every review article comes with limitations. Just to mention one, our focus on research published in English inevitably leaves some gaps. We hope that this review will encourage researchers to extend and replicate our theoretical framework more broadly to address any areas we might have missed.

Supra-politics

By *supra-politics*, we refer to the overarching role of global norms in shaping wildfire narratives and management. These norms filter through different levels of governance via international institutions, formal agreements, and funding mechanisms that establish common standards. As a policy domain, supra-politics extends beyond state sovereignty and is not confined to state actors. In our conceptualization, it represents the outer concentric circle influencing the politics of wildfires, but this does not suggest that supra-political norms wield less influence than those from the inner circles. In fact, these norms are crucial in defining the contours of fire policy regimes, thereby exerting direct effects on attitudes towards fire and fire management strategies at the national and sub-national level. This is particularly true in the context of power unbalances that characterise global geopolitics. Indeed, in the Global South, supra-politics influence on policy formulation often raises issues of fairness and equity, bringing colonial-era legacies into the conversation. This section outlines how supra-politics comes into play by mapping the intricate interaction between global norms and local realities.

As with many other environmental challenges that puzzle humanity, wildfires are frequently characterised as “wicked problems” whose management is complicated by “feedback [loops], dynamic thresholds, and uncertainties transcending temporal, spatial, and functional boundaries” (Kirschner et al. 2023). From a political standpoint, these complex challenges not only involve coordination issues across jurisdictions and actors but, more critically, tensions between different knowledge and value systems. As introduced by Rittel and Webber (1973), wicked problems are distinct from tame technical problems because they have no finite set of solutions and no definite way to test them: “there is no definitive formulation of a wicked problem [because] the information needed to *understand* the problem depends upon one’s idea for *solving* it” (ibidem: 161). As a result, solutions cannot be judged objectively as true or false, as they are shaped by the diverse interests of the parties involved, “their special value-sets, and their ideological predilections” (ibidem: 163). This consideration is central to wildfire politics for various reasons, which we explore below. In essence, it is often the case that technocratic discourses surrounding biomass burning emissions and forest

conservation play a key role in shaping fire management interventions in the Global South, which are frequently attuned at the institutional level but resisted or bypassed by local communities.

Fire governance lacks a unified global framework and instead operates within a polycentric system, often characterized by uncoordinated responses across different scales and stakeholders (Carmenta et al. 2017). Consequently, the global response to wildfires is shaped by a patchwork of initiatives, ranging from international and regional agreements to national level strategies. Among these, two overarching and partly overlapping frameworks – disaster risk reduction and climate change mitigation – exert considerable influence over fire governance. This influence is evident in the growing attention to fire-related threats across global institutional agendas and planning instruments. In the first place, wildfire hazards are incorporated into the mandates of various IGOs and are embedded in broader disaster risk reduction strategies (e.g., UNDRR 2017). Within the UN system, an inter-agency Working Group on Wildland Fire was established in 2001 under the *International Strategy for Disaster Reduction* to facilitate policy dialogue and collaboration between agencies and programs. More recently, UNDRR-UNEP's *Nature-based Solutions for Disaster Risk Reduction* (2021), which supports the implementation of the Sendai Framework, emphasizes integrated fire management as a crucial component of land management strategies aimed at reducing the risk of “wildfire disasters”.

Under climate policy, wildfires are increasingly addressed within the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) due to their role in greenhouse gas emissions and carbon cycle disruptions. The UNFCCC has emerged as a key policy platform where fire management intersects with climate change goals, particularly through initiatives such as REDD+ (Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation). As anthropogenic climate change intensifies, it is expected to increase drought risk and alter fuel configurations in many regions (Cammelli & Angelsen 2019; Kelly et al. 2020), particularly in tropical forests where more frequent and extreme fires could drastically disrupt ecosystem regeneration (Stephens et al. 2014). These changing conditions, along with shifts in climate patterns, create considerable uncertainty about future fire activity (Duane et al. 2021). At the same time, wildfires are under scrutiny for their role in releasing greenhouse gases, particulate matter, and other pollutants (Keywood et al. 2013). According to some estimates, fires in the Brazilian Amazon release more CO₂ than the entire Brazilian energy sector and reduce forest carbon stock by up to 40% (Cammelli et al. 2020), with emissions from drought-induced fires exceeding those from deforestation (Aragão et al. 2018). These figures should be interpreted carefully as they mix two different types of emissions: while CO₂ from fires is essentially a re-emission of previously atmospheric carbon, fossil fuel combustion adds new carbon that has been stored underground for millions of years (Belcher 2013: 11). Misunderstanding this distinction can lead to misplaced responsibility, as biomass combustion is part of the biogenic carbon cycle. Nonetheless, wildfire narratives and policies are increasingly integrated into emission abatement schemes.

Piloted in Australia, where prescribed burns in northern savannas were shifted from the late dry to the early dry season (Crocker et al. 2023a), emissions abatement projects have been praised as effective community-based methods for achieving carbon offsets in many fire-prone countries, especially in sub-Saharan Africa (Lipsett-Moore et al. 2018). Savanna fire management programs aimed at generating carbon credits are viewed as providing “potential win-win-win solutions” to meet mitigation targets, enhance biodiversity conservation, and benefit local communities while addressing chronic underfunding (Tear et al. 2021). It has been noted that not all savanna landscapes are suited

for economically viable community offset enterprises, and significant efforts are needed to ensure these offsets can be effectively traded in carbon markets (Russell-Smith et al. 2017). However, challenges in scaling up carbon financing projects overshadow broader concerns about growing reliance on market-based tools in environmental policy, such as payments for ecosystem services (PES) promoted in the context of REDD+ schemes (Jefferson et al. 2020). These concerns include the possibility that an economic approach may have negative social and ecological consequences (Moura et al. 2019), such as socially inappropriate land management practices (Barlow et al. 2012), or a failure to differentiate between large-scale agro-industrial clearing and smallholder subsistence burning, leading to misinterpretations of place-based fire dependence (Eloy et al., 2019a). Although indigenous communities may be included as “implementers” (Mistry et al., 2016), a major criticism is that such blueprint policies support an anti-fire discourse “[discriminating] against customary smallholder farmers and their modes of production, culture and lifeways” (Carmenta et al. 2021: 9). In brief, global conservation efforts are viewed as being compromised by a technocratic bias, excluding ‘non-experts’ from developing practical policy solutions, and favouring an economic bias that limits acceptable options to those that can be quantified in monetary terms (Dewulf 2013).

Critiques of market-based tools fit within the expanding body of research on neoliberal environmental governance and the financialization of climate policy (Ciplet & Roberts 2017). However, fire control strategies shaped by the global conservation discourse continue to reflect colonial-era misconceptions about the presumed benefit of preserving tropical landscapes in a pristine state (Welch et al. 2013). Recent literature on fire management in the Global South underscores a sharp divide between policy communities and local landholders, exposing fundamental differences in ideology, worldviews, and values (Carmenta et al. 2017). In the Brazilian Amazon, for instance, subsidies and credit restrictions tied to fire bans have exacerbated inequalities and disempowered marginalised fire users (Cammelli et al. 2020). Nonetheless, evidence suggests that traditional land management practices, including controlled burning, have more effectively preserved tropical savannah (*cerrado*) landscape and supported vegetational recovery compared to non-indigenous methods (Welch et al., 2013; see also Berlinck & Batista 2020). While technocratic approaches to fire governance often promise win-win solutions, the trade-offs involved limit the feasibility of achieving equitable solutions for all (Miller et al. 2022). Viewed from this perspective, global fire management is not just a governance challenge but a contested policy arena where ‘zero fire’ narratives privilege some types of knowledge and expertise over others (Sletto 2008). Research on social equity in fire ecology tend to concur that conservation policies often suppress non-scientific knowledge and the social practices of the communities that hold such knowledge (Vazquez et al. 2022).

While this process occurs in both developed and developing regions, in the latter it is often influenced by a lingering Eurocentric bias that echoes neo-colonial tropes. In the early-twentieth century, colonial authorities established exclusionary protected areas and implemented fire suppression policies, decrying burning practices as major causes of deforestation and degradation. European foresters and botanists promoted the belief that the savanna biome resulted from desiccation and land erosion caused by grasslands burning (Pooley 2018). This misguided understanding led to the displacement of indigenous peoples and the disruption of local fire regimes. Despite this historical baggage, anti-fire narratives have persisted, continuing to frame local fire use as destructive and unsustainable (Fairhead & Leach 1996; Pyne 1997; Kull 2004; Laris 2004; Eriksen 2007; Dressler 2009). The cultural shaming of subsistence burning (Welch & Coimbra 2021) has altered the spatial-temporal distribution of fires,

leading to paradoxical outcomes such as the concentration of high-intensity wildfires within protected areas due to the accumulation of flammable biomass (Crocker et al. 2023a). Carmenta et al. (2021) pointedly note that the lack of an environmental justice perspective in this discourse casts smallholder farmers as “environmental villains” damaging their own lands, which justifies restrictive measures against traditional fallowing methods while supporting industrialised agriculture. On a deeper level, as discussed in the following section, this dynamic has reinforced the racialization of marginalised identities and supported territorial consolidation by state power.

International aid and development funding are primary mechanisms for disseminating and institutionalising supranational norms in the Global South. In the context of fire management, UN agencies, environmental NGOs, regional organisations, and research institutes act as norm entrepreneurs, setting standards for global governance (Finnemore 1996). As environmental protection is increasingly framed as a key state responsibility within the global discourse on good governance and sustainable development, this strengthens the normative influence of transnational actors, especially in countries that have long been under colonial rule. This external influence is frequently accepted, driven not only by the desire to secure funding but also by the pursuit of international legitimacy. Smith et al. (2023) illustrate how fire management strategies in post-colonial Belize and Guyana are strongly shaped by global environmental narratives that, despite adopting rhetoric around community-based or traditional management, continue to frame rural fire use in tropical savannas as problematic. In both countries, dependence on external funding has led state agencies, conservation NGOs, and indigenous advocacy groups to tailor their approaches to meet the expectations of international donors, with significant input from foreign governments and consultants. Consequently, these policies and projects have often had limited impact and endorsement, as fire suppression strategies struggle to match local realities.

The aforementioned study on Central America is no exception. Bassett and Zuéli (2000) noted historical parallels between colonial-era and contemporary environmental planning in the context of the National Environmental Action Plan promoted by the World Bank in Côte d’Ivoire. They observed that both eras place blame on farmers and herders for land degradation and propose increased state intervention, including the exclusion of local people from protected areas. Although the number of stakeholders involved in environmental planning has undoubtedly increased since the 1930s, Bassett and Zuéli argued that the perspectives of ordinary people remain marginalised. This “green conditionality” in the aid and loan disbursement is viewed as a form of coercion, leading developing countries in savanna regions to adopt fire suppression policies promoted by the metropole, rather than creating fire management strategies suited to local environments (Eriksen 2007). Along these lines, political ecology research on anthropogenic fire in the Global South highlights the clash between different ontologies of nature (Vazquez et al. 2022). Although it involves power imbalances and natural resource control, the neglect of indigenous knowledge can manifest in seemingly technical decisions, such as the selection of tree species for forest restoration, whereby economic preferences for fast-growing species like eucalyptus and conifers (which are generally more flammable than native vegetation) ultimately increase fire risk (Duane et al. 2021; Luna-Celino & Kainer 2024). Misunderstanding fire behaviour in specific biomes – such as the misclassification of savannas as degraded forests (Tornorsam et al. 2024) – undermines effective conservation planning and priority setting. Unsurprisingly, fire management strategies focused on suppression have proven

unsustainable, leaving countries to face the dual challenge of costly, ineffective responses and widespread damage from uncontrolled fires (Dube 2013).

From the examples provided, it is evident that considering supra-politics as a key policy constituency is essential to (re)politicise fire research across the Global South. To be sure, the spread of global norms should not be seen exclusively as a tool for displacing and dispossessing powerless communities. Similarly, it would be just as inaccurate to romanticise indigenous and local knowledge as inherently fair and equitable without acknowledging the power dynamics within agrarian societies. Nonetheless, the technocratic managerialism characterising global fire governance often reveals a colonial gaze that seeks to “fix the Third World” through white saviorism, fostering a narrative of deficiency while expecting *resilient* locals to adapt to prescribed solutions and comply as development subjects (Sultana 2022). A glaring example of climate coloniality is the irony of assigning indigenous peoples the responsibility of offsetting a significant share of the global carbon budget through REDD+ projects funded by high-emission industrialised countries, which are notably reluctant to transform their own production systems in the first place (Welch et al. 2013). In other words, epistemic violence in knowledge production – and its propagation through global frameworks and institutions – is a fundamental aspect of wildfire supra-politics.

State-politics

The colonial encounter between settlers’ scientific presumptions and indigenous burning practices is a key focus in the environmental historiography of European colonialism (Pooley 2018). Imperial powers employed fire to conquer new territories, usurp land rights, and facilitate resource extraction (Ulloa & Barton 2024). As discussed earlier, the legacies of colonial rule are still evident in many post-colonial countries, where they have been ingrained in bureaucratic systems and reinforced through the conditionality of international aid. This persistence highlights that harnessing fire – whether through restriction or control – has long been a fundamental strategy of territorialization. Unlike the broader concept of the production of space, territorialization refers specifically to the act of claiming territory (Peluso & Lund 2011). This process establishes and sustains power relations “among governed environmental subjects and between subjects and authorities” (ibidem: 673). Regulating (or deregulating) landscape burning, in particular, is part of the modern state’s toolkit for rationalising and organising space, and all the activities and relations within it, into a legible, governable territory.

The removal or insertion of fire is, indeed, a powerful means of demarcation, with consequences for land relations, including the restructuring and reinforcement of legal authority. Since the 16th-century enclosures in England – an early transformation of land into a commodity for mass consumption and capital accumulation – fire has played an instrumental role in establishing new systems of knowledge production and population control. Enclosed land linked agricultural “improvement” to European and urban bourgeois superiority (Marzec 2015). This rationale supported the emergence of state security mechanisms rooted in contractualist political theories, which viewed true freedom as the escape from the dangers and unpredictability of the state of nature (ibidem). Marzec further argues that this shift also influenced subject formation, replacing communal inhabitancy with more hierarchical relationships – such as “landlord/labourer” or “propertied/dispossessed” – which were later mirrored in colonial dynamics and laid the groundwork for contemporary systems of environmental management. In this light, the enclosure movement was not just an agricultural reform, but a

precursor to colonial practices and modern state control. As Neumann pointed out in his work on wilderness enclosures in Africa, “the containment and control of nature in conservation territories [were] inseparable from the colonizing state’s efforts to control its African subjects and ultimately create a new kind of person: civilized, productive, and observable” (2004: 203-4). As part of broader territorialization practices (e.g., land surveys, property rights, commercial concessions, economic zoning), fire management serves as a method for asserting control over a landscape. More specifically, it dictates which activities or spatial uses are permitted within designated territories (Shattuk & Peluso 2021).

These insights build on extensive scholarship that has underscored the fundamental connection between state-building, territoriality, and the appropriation of nature. Whitehead et al. (2007: 2) refer to ‘state nature’ as “a form of territorially framed and administratively governed nature, which has been brought into existence as part of the processes that have resulted in the formation of modern nation-states”. Drawing on Foucault, the nation-state is conceptualised as a governmental entity characterised by a rational science of government – one that involves the methodical gathering of data about the population and territory it seeks to govern. A key takeaway from their theory is that the state’s framing of nature invariably entails the violent extrication of nature from its ecological context. This is most evident in wildfire politics, as demonstrated by the limitations of the fire suppression paradigm⁴.

By *state-politics*, we indicate a second analytical layer that focuses specifically on how states regulate fire. Rather than offering a systematic typology of common policy interventions, this approach considers fire management as a political-symbolic instrument that delineates the boundaries of capital accumulation and shapes political subject formation within the sovereign space of the state. Given that state territorialities are contested arenas, intersecting with livelihoods and collective identities, fire policies and legislation can reveal underlying political dynamics, much like smoke rising from a seemingly flame-free patch of land signals a smouldering fire beneath.

From this viewpoint, Vandergeest and Peluso’s extensive work (1995, 2006, 2011, 2015, 2020) on *political forests* provides a key reference for understanding how the state asserts territorial sovereignty through the scientific, bureaucratic, and institutional practices of forestry. They emphasise that defining what qualifies as forest – by including or excluding specific tree species and territorial zones – places demarcated land under the jurisdiction of state agencies, thereby enabling control over the use and access of natural resources. This results in a new form of politics that challenges customary rights, often leading to displacement and dispossession of resident populations. Therefore, the centralisation of forestry under national or provincial authorities has frequently contributed to the emergence of “violent environments” (Peluso & Watts 2001), stemming from disputes over resource governance. In their genealogy of professional state forestry, Vandergeest and

⁴ Fire suppression paradigm refers to a dominant fire management approach that emphasizes the complete prevention, control, and extinguishing of all fires (Keywood et al. 2013: 24) – often through centralized, top-down strategies aimed at protecting life, property, and landscapes. This paradigm has been criticized for neglecting ecological contexts, as prolonged suppression in fire-adapted ecosystems can increase fuel loads and the risk of severe fires (Busenberg 2004; Jensen 2006; Harrison et al. 2021). It also creates or exacerbates social tensions with local communities that depend on controlled burning for their livelihoods (Eloy et al. 2019a; Moura et al. 2019).

Peluso (2015) further highlight that technical expertise was developed to “predict, control, eliminate, or stimulate certain ecological processes”, with the aim of transforming or maintaining forest ecologies at specific growth stages to fulfil social, economic, or political objectives. In this context, fire emerges as a key socio-ecological process that the state claims as its own.

Another noteworthy aspect of their analysis is that the creation of political forests unfolded across three historical moments. First, during territorial colonialism (early 19th century to 1930s), colonial powers established forestry departments, relocating local communities and converting subversive “jungles” into controlled forests. The second phase (1945–1970s) involved “forestry for development” programs, largely driven by international agencies such as FAO, which expanded scientific forestry practices and criminalized swidden agriculture by blaming it for deforestation. The third phase, influenced by post-WWII insurgencies, saw governments employ violence to transform contested jungles into political forests, further entrenching the separation of agriculture and forest areas. The fourth and ongoing phase, marked by the involvement of non-state actors in forest management, is discussed in greater detail in the following section. Together, these phases highlight the interplay between external pressures and internal dynamics in shaping political forests. In the Global South, post-colonial states were often required to balance state-building with the pursuit of international legitimacy, making forest governance a critical site for asserting and enacting sovereignty vis-à-vis both domestic and global constituencies.

A recent study by Ulloa and Barton (2024) explores the territorial significance of fire through a historical political ecology of the Wallmapu-Araucanía region in Chile. They argue that “pyropolitics” serves both politico-symbolic and techno-productive functions aimed at controlling and dominating nature. In settler societies, the colonial state used fire to intimidate, destroy, and clear land for agricultural and industrial development. This process of territorialization not only reshaped landscapes for economic exploitation but also erased cultural and ecological histories, creating a *tabula rasa* for capital accumulation and the expansion of private property. Ulloa and Barton identify three major historical phases in this process. During the colonialization period, fire facilitated the incorporation of Wallmapu-Araucanía into the Chilean Republic. This entailed the imposition of a new property regime in militarily occupied territories, displacing Mapuche indigenous people in urban centers or confining them to limited communal spaces. From 1890 to 1990, fire was used more intensively to clear land for agriculture, benefiting settlers from Europe and other parts of Chile, while further marginalizing the Mapuche. The third phase, which extends to the present days, sees fire appropriated as a tool of resistance by Mapuche organisations against large landholders, to which the state has responded by labelling these groups as terrorists and militarising the region. In sum, fire in Wallmapu-Araucanía continues to serve both symbolic and practical objectives in the ongoing struggle for territorial control. What distinguishes Ulloa and Barton’s analysis is their recognition that fire is not only a coercive instrument wielded by the state to marginalise and dispossess indigenous people – portrayed as a landless “other” and a threat to property – but also an effective means of resistance and de-territorialization mobilised by the oppressed to confront the enduring legacies of colonisation. This latter dimension will be further explored in the section on infra-politics.

Among the various implications of these territorial practices, a recurring theme in the literature is that the sanctioning of fire use in many post-colonial countries has defined indigenous-state relations in a way that associates environmental blame with indigeneity (Carmenta et al. 2021). Smith and Dressler

(2020: 4) offer a compelling example, illustrating how public portrayals of swidden cultivators (*kaingineros*) by government authorities and national media in the Philippines continue to reflect “sedimented histories of racialized violence”, which cast non-Christian minority groups as environmental threats. Indigenous upland communities are stereotyped as relying on fire-dependent agriculture, and their use of fire framed as ecologically destructive. This narrative is common in Southeast Asia, where cultural differences are often articulated through the upland-lowland divide, and minority groups are accused of degrading state-owned, mountainous forests (Vandergeest 2003; Wittayapak 2008; Hares 2009; Baird et al. 2017; Mostafanezhad & Evrard 2021). Smith and Dressler emphasise that the racialization (or tribalization) of fire use as a problem tied to ethnicity obscures the role of more powerful state and corporate actors in environmental degradation. Their analysis further demonstrates that state-indigenous relations have remained largely consistent with colonial-era dynamics, with community-based natural resource management often functioning as a mechanism of social control rather than genuine empowerment.

This highlights the co-production of identity politics and environmental policies in the shadow of the state. Political forests emerge as “particular constellation[s] of power constituted by ideas, practices and institutions that seek to regulate peoples’ access to resources, providing recognition and legitimacy to some, whilst excluding and criminalizing others” (Elmhirst 2011: 173). The widespread use of derogatory terms like “arsonists” or “pyromaniacs” to vilify traditional burning practices is common in tropical and savanna regions, leading to bans and accusations of reckless burning that intersect with ethnic classification (Mistry et al. 2016; Bilbao et al. 2019). This occurs despite research indicating that indigenous knowledge can help prevent large wildfires. Experiential knowledge enables local communities to distinguish between productive and unproductive fire regimes, thereby enhancing their ability to promote biodiversity and mitigate the risk of catastrophic fires through the creation of mosaic patterns of burned and unburned vegetation (Butz, 2009). However, the rampant “pyrophobia” (Eloy et al. 2019a) and the increasing focus on fire suppression obscure a very different reality: the transformation of indigenous ecosystems into agricultural and livestock production systems (Bilbao et al. 2019). Market expansion and forestry policies are interconnected forces reshaping fire regimes across the Global South. In this respect, racialization becomes a key component of territorial strategies, “not only by creating subject categories, but by attaching racialised subjects to exclusive territories and usufruct rights” (Devine & Baca 2020: 13).

The works discussed above illuminate how fire makes visible the constitutive relationship between cultural hegemony and territoriality, underscoring the state’s role in producing authoritative knowledge as central to its exercise of power. From an epistemological perspective, however, the state should not be reified as a monolithic entity with inherent authority. Post-structuralist scholarship, in particular, has demonstrated the analytical value of treating the state not as a singular, sovereign agent but as a set of contingent practices and discourses enacted by a multiplicity of actors and institutions. Although research on the governmentality of fire has shed light on the ways in which colonial and post-colonial institutions shape subjectivities, it has often overlooked the micropolitical dynamics at play. A notable exception is Mathews’ (2005) ethnographic analysis of everyday practices within the Mexican forest service. As in other contexts, Mexican government officials have condemned slash-and-burn agriculture, blaming it for deforestation and pushing for strict fire regulations. This discourse reflects a familiar pattern where negative stereotypes of certain groups are leveraged to legitimise state authority. However, Mathews offers a counterintuitive insight,

suggesting that “state power may depend upon the management of ignorance and knowledge by officials and their clients” (ibidem: 796). His institutional ethnography exposes a disconnect between those who design fire management policies and those tasked with enforcing them. The Mexican forest service, historically underfunded and frequently reorganised, has struggled to enforce policies that are often impractical (since fire is essential to agriculture and pastoralism in many areas), yet continues to uphold long-standing ideologies about fire prevention. Despite these contradictions, regulations persist as means to maintaining symbolic capital, granting foresters discretionary power to selectively punish violations and forcing rural communities to act in secrecy. This creates zones of illegibility and ignorance, in which field-level foresters assert their authority through daily interactions with both clients and higher-level officials, who remain largely unaware of the actual extent of fire activity. The tension between official policies and local adjustments does not challenge the state’s sovereignty but provides a glimpse beneath the surface of formal institutions, regulations, and policies, which is the focus of next sections.

Para-politics

Critical geography has long underlined the danger of falling into the “territorial trap” of state-centrism (Agnew 1994), which can obscure sub-state and trans-state scalar dynamics. This same oversight would impair our understanding of the dense milieu of relations that define the politics of wildfires. To address this, we propose a third analytical layer: *para-politics*. Para-politics investigates “the relationships between the public state and the political processes and arrangements outside and beyond conventional politics” (Wilson 2012: 3). It challenges Weberian orthodoxy by exploring covert, extra-legal forms of sovereignty that operate alongside the overt politics of the public state. In other words, it highlights the influence of entities not formally part of the state, yet nonetheless significant in shaping political outcomes under conditions of diminished accountability. These entities can be as different as business interests, military elites, security firms, criminal organisations, and grassroots movements. The concept is often deployed in discussions of the “dual-state” (Sakwa 2010; Sooyler 2015), which emphasises the coexistence of an official legal system with parallel, unofficial power structures operating outside formal legality. In this review article, we broaden the category to include social activism and advocacy networks to capture a wider spectrum of political influence.

Territoriality is not the exclusive domain of the state. As previously noted, Vandergeest and Peluso (2015) describe the current fourth moment in the history of political forests as characterised by the increased participation of non-state actors, such as international NGOs, private corporations, and forest-based communities. Devine and Baca (2020) further elaborate on this contemporary phase, which they label “green neoliberalism”, and expand on Vandergeest and Peluso’s observation that global conservation efforts have remade political forests into “charismatic forests” requiring protection. This transformation not only changes the perceived value of forests but also shifts that value from a national to a global scale. Reconceptualizing forests as global lungs and carbon sinks – assets to be protected and harnessed within climate policies – exemplifies this shift. The discourse on climate change has produced moral and scientific claims about forest governance on behalf of humanity, “introducing more non-state actors like global conservation organisations, non-profit foundations, and celebrity philanthropists into positions of forestry expertise” (ibid.: 11). Emerging from the premise of state failure and inefficiency, green neoliberalism promotes market mechanisms as alternative solutions. This rationale is accompanied by new disciplinary and governmental

technologies that restructure socio-natural relations. Devine and Baca cite eco-tourism development, community forestry, and the provision of ecosystem services as key neoliberal practices that contribute to the creation of “pluralised political forests”. Green neoliberalism does not signal the demise of the state in forest management but rather illustrates that the contentious co-production of political forests now involves a broader array of actors operating across multiple scales.

A para-political lens on wildfire politics examines the informal configurations of power that influence fire ignition patterns and fire policy decisions. One of the most prominent dimensions discussed in the literature is the role of patronage networks and entrenched foreign investment (Goldstein 2019). A key reference in this field is Varkkey’s research (2013, 2014, 2015) on patronage politics within Indonesia’s oil palm sector and its connection to transboundary haze in Southeast Asia. Her study reconstructs how peat fires are frequently linked to illegal land-clearing by commercial oil palm plantations. Despite legal bans on the use of fire for this purpose, both local and foreign companies often operate with impunity due to strong ties with political elites. These patronage networks undermine the enforcement of environmental regulations, enabling companies to adopt cost-cutting methods such as open burning, despite the environmental and socioeconomic harm. Varkkey untangles the web of connections that facilitate rent-seeking behaviour and disregard for burning regulations. These include the appointment of former senior bureaucrats with government connections to top management positions in plantation firms, repeated parliamentary attempts to hold landowners accountable for fires blocked by powerful lobbies, and the widespread practice of companies hiring subcontractors or labourers to conduct illegal burning, thus avoiding direct liability. Additionally, decentralisation reforms have led to institutional confusion regarding which level of government is responsible for addressing fire-related crimes. As a result, transboundary haze represents a classic collective action problem, in which the benefits of patronage-driven practices for a few individuals outweigh the broader societal need for environmental protection.

Peat swamps become highly flammable when drained for commercial purposes such as oil palm or pulpwood production. Since fire remains the most cost-effective and accessible method for clearing and preparing land (Purnomo et al. 2017), the profitability of peatland conversion has led to uncontrolled fires. Peatland fires release significantly more toxic haze and carbon emissions compared to fires on mineral soils (Jefferson et al. 2020). The economic and health impacts have been severe, with estimate costs reaching over \$4.5 billion in 1997–98 and \$16 billion in 2015, along with thousands of premature deaths due to respiratory infections (Edwards et al. 2020). As the haze spreads across borders, the impact is not limited to Indonesia but creates a recurrent regional pollution crisis. This has caused tensions between Indonesia and neighbouring countries such as Singapore, Malaysia, and Thailand. Despite transboundary cooperation on haze mitigation at the ASEAN level, patronage networks extend beyond national borders as well, obstructing effective policy coordination. Varkkey argues that the consensus-oriented norms defining the “ASEAN Way” have sidelined environmental concerns in favour of economic interests. The emphasis on national sovereignty within ASEAN allows individual states to selectively commit to collective initiatives without disrupting regional consensus. Varkkey contends that this approach has fostered a free-rider problem, where “the importance of the palm oil industry to the Indonesian economy, coupled with the vested interests cultivated among elites in the sector, takes priority over the well-being of Indonesian, Malaysian, and Singaporean society, which continue to suffer annually as a result of haze” (2014: 8). In her analysis of the discussions leading to the ASEAN Agreement on Transboundary Haze Pollution, she observes that the

issue of illegal burning by plantation companies was never brought to the negotiating table. This omission was not only favourable to Indonesian business elites, but also to Malaysian and Singaporean companies heavily involved in Indonesia's oil palm industry.

This example demonstrates that the transnational ramifications of clientelist networks can foster a rent-seeking environment in which land-clearing through fire generates profits for well-connected elites and their associates. In contexts where patronage politics is influential, fires often emerge as an epiphenomenon of collusion between state and corporate actors in land use and resource capture (Purnomo et al. 2019). The presence of similar elite-driven patterns of forest exploitation across Southeast Asia challenges the notion that the colonial legacy is still the primary cause of forest degradation in the region (Ansori 2021). Although fire-related research on these para-political dynamics remains in the early stages, the pioneering studies referenced here provide compelling evidence of the crucial role elites play in creating fire-prone landscapes, often in conjunction with corporate agribusiness expansion. As McCarthy (2002) noted in his study of illegal logging in Sumatra, informal arrangements can navigate around contradictions in formal legal systems, especially when state policies conflict with customary authority. In areas where state enforcement is weak and power is highly localised, state agents often straddle the line between formality and informality: by leveraging their gatekeeping roles, they extract rents to sustain networks of exchange and accommodation that serve the interests of various actors. In their study of the political economy of fires in Riau province, Purnomo et al. (2017) found that various actors along the value chain benefited from land clearing, with profits primarily going to district-level local elites and community members involved in the burning process, all protected by a patronage network.

Goldstein (2019) argues that the transnational nature of material accumulation in contemporary political forests blurs the conventional state/non-state binary. However, discussions about fire culpability in Indonesia often overlook the role of extra-state actors responsible for peatland drainage. In fact, the primary culprits of peat fires are the multinational corporations managing agribusiness plantations, with a chain of command extending from overseas investors to plantation managers, who can easily deflect blame onto peasant communities practising swidden agriculture. Goldstein notes that this rhetoric is intentionally vague, failing to account for the diverse range of motivations behind fire ignition within rural areas. To reference a previously mentioned study, Purnomo et al. (2017) distinguish at least 20 types of stakeholders with varying interests in land and forest fires. Goldstein suggests that understanding contemporary forest politics requires a re-evaluation of spatial dynamics, considering the vertical and volumetric dimensions of forest territories. A three-dimensional approach, she argues, is better suited to analyse the changing materiality of forests and the involvement of actors beyond the state. Goldstein also critiques the limitations of aerial photography and satellite remote sensing, which struggle to capture the full volumetric scope of peat fires, thereby perpetuating patterns of blame and responsibility avoidance that facilitate ongoing economic control over forest areas. Since territorial disputes are intertwined with representational practices, this serves as a methodological reminder to map power asymmetries without resorting to binary reductions that fail to grasp the complexity of the context.

Although Indonesia provides an ideal case for examining this “complex institutional matrix” (McCarthy 2002), such complexity is not unique to this country. For example, the influence of the *fazendeiros* (a powerful rural agribusiness lobby) has been highlighted in the Brazilian parliament, where they have

pushed to weaken environmental regulations in order to expand soybean farming and mining (Bilbao et al. 2019). Extending this research trajectory to other geographic contexts is crucial for establishing a comparative framework, especially considering that burning practices are culturally situated and influenced by kinship, political, ethnic, and religious factors. For instance, Eriksen (2007) explains that in Zambia's customary lands, where traditional authorities hold control, late dry season burning is mandated by the local chief to foster caterpillar breeding. The chief, who financially benefits from the caterpillar harvest, has a vested interest in promoting these fires, while villagers face sanctions if they start fires outside of the chief's directives. This scenario illustrates how traditional leadership and local economic interests can shape environmental practices, often with minimal oversight from state institutions. Consequently, it underscores the importance of adopting a broad perspective to examine the interplay between formal and informal power structures. Decentering a political ecology approach from the state proves compelling, as it facilitates a more comprehensive exploration of both the distributive and identity implications of wildfire politics.

Infra-politics

To this point, we have examined political dynamics that, although not always visible, are enacted by hegemonic actors and institutionalised within decision-making processes. We have also seen that fire management approaches frequently marginalize subaltern groups, especially rural peasantries, through a range of mechanisms from political exclusion to outright criminalisation. Incorporating the agency of these marginalised groups is essential for a comprehensive understanding of wildfire politics. This necessitates a fourth analytical dimension, which we designate as *infra-politics*. Scott describes this concept as encompassing "a wide variety of low-profile forms of resistance that dare not speak in their own name" (1990: 19). Based on earlier research on peasant resistance in Malaysia (1985), Scott developed an analytical framework to capture "the often fugitive political conduct of subordinate groups" (ibid.: xii). The central idea is that, instead of direct confrontation or rebellion, powerless groups publicly reinforce the appearance of conformity to the hierarchical order imposed by ruling elites, while privately offering a veiled critique of power "spoken behind the back of the dominant". The boundary between public and hidden transcripts of power relations becomes a battleground of everyday struggles, where both elites and subordinates continually negotiate what is visible and what is concealed. *Infra-politics* highlights the subtle, often opaque forms of resistance that occur in secluded settings, where the oppressed seem silenced and open defiance is undetected. Scott argues that by focusing solely on overt political activity, we overlook "the immense political terrain that lies between quiescence and revolt and that, for better or worse, is the political environment of subject classes" (ibid.: 199). This perspective reveals that even symbolic resistance is closely linked to practical efforts to resist or mitigate material exploitation.

Tellingly, Scott identifies arson as one of the many stratagems that the powerless can employ against those in power. The anonymous and unpredictable nature of fire, combined with its iconography, makes it a "trump card" for marginalised peasants (Kull 2002b). Research has long recognised rural incendiary as a tool of protest or resistance (Prochaska 1986; Peluso 1992; Pyne 1997; Kuhlken 1999; Kull 2002a, 2002b; Laris 2004). Kuhlken (1999) observes that arson is more common in regions where fire plays a crucial ecological or cultural role, often becoming a last resort for communities that have lost control over vital resources or are forced to abandon traditional livelihoods. Kull (2002b) concurs, noting that incendiary reactions are frequently triggered by anti-fire restrictions and a sense

of moral injustice. In Madagascar, both during colonial and post-colonial periods, prohibitions on traditional burning practices were seen as violations of customary rights, prompting Malagasy peasants to continue burning as a means of asserting their land rights.

Kull argues that resistance is influenced not only by the type of domination, as noted by Peluso (1992), but also by a “landed moral economy”; a concept borrowed from Neumann (1998) that refers to how “people’s expectations of subsistence rights – and thus their resistance – are based on both historically specific social relations and localised conditions of resource availability” (2002b: 15). Given that rural societies are divided along various lines, resistance strategies may stem from internal disputes rather than solely from opposition to state laws. Tensions between herders and farmers over land management provide a case in point (Kpienbaareh & Luginaah 2019). Kull categorises resistance into two main approaches: advantage-taking, where fire is used for practical purposes like pasture or agricultural production, with resistance being a secondary effect; and protest, which aims to change state policies or decriminalise practices through legal or overt means. Determining whether fires represent overt protest, strategic advantage, or a mix of both is challenging. Kull suggests that the primary motive behind most fires is practical livelihood needs rather than political protest. Although these actions may implicitly challenge state restrictions, the main intent is often tied to material needs rather than symbolic protest. Echoing Fairhead and Leach (1996), he emphasises that resistance typically targets the material impacts of state policies rather than the broader anti-fire rhetoric of the state.

Recent studies, however, have focused on the growing weaponization of fire. As noted earlier, in the case of Mapuche organisations in Wallmapu-Araucanía, fire has been used as a form of resistance to reclaim traditional lands and restore indigenous ways of life (Ulloa & Barton, 2024). The burning of churches, forestry assets, and logging vehicles in recent years is part of a long-standing confrontation that dates back to the early Spanish conquest. In response, the Chilean government has enforced the Anti-Terrorism Law and deployed specialised military forces, further intensifying the conflict. Between 2016 and 2021, there were 132 arson attacks, primarily in the regions where the Mapuche were originally displaced. Another relevant study is Chance’s research (2015) on how state-citizen conflicts in South Africa continue to be mediated by fire. During apartheid, fire symbolised both the regime’s brutality and the potential for liberation, becoming a weapon used by all sides. Chance points out that this legacy persists in post-apartheid South Africa, where residents of townships and informal settlements still use fire in their struggles against neoliberal policies and inequality. As in the past, fire remains a tool for the urban poor to disrupt state institutions, block roads, and draw attention to marginalised spaces, maintaining its dual role as a symbol of destruction and resistance. These studies emphasise that fire can mediate conflicts between the state and insurgent or oppressed groups. Similarly, Dinc et al. (2021) suggest that forest fires in Dersim province surged dramatically after the breakdown of the peace process between the Turkish state and the Kurdistan Workers’ Party (PKK). They also note that media coverage was shaped by political affiliations, with right-wing and pro-government outlets often choosing not to report on the fires.

Even in polarised settings, broad terms like *state* or *insurgents* can obscure the diverse and sometimes conflicting interests within these aggregates. Kull (2002b) illustrates this by indicating that the push to enforce anti-fire policies in Madagascar was led by “an elite portion of the state”, specifically government technocrats from the capital and their allies. Similarly, Mathews (2005) details that local

forestry officials in Oaxaca downplayed a new fire control regulation due to limited resources and concerns over community relations. Instead of confronting central authority, these officials opted for tactical silence, avoiding public criticism while quietly accommodating community needs. This exemplifies a form of de facto autonomy, where local authorities navigate their circumstances while maintaining an outward façade of compliance, reflecting the tension between central directives and local realities. In this light, Kull's call to incorporate ambiguities and context into analyses of domination and resistance is particularly fitting, as it acknowledges complexities and contradictions in state-peasant relations.

In summary, incendiarism can become a form of subtle resistance for expressing dissent or contesting authority, particularly when formal channels are unavailable and traditional burning is restricted or criminalised. By defying these regulations, individuals or groups assert political agency against the imposition of land management systems by external actors. Whether aimed at the state or specific policies, the defiance through fire underscores the fact that fire is integral to both subsistence and cultural expression, making its complete suppression unrealistic (Sletto 2008; Bilbao et al. 2010; Mistry et al. 2016; Eloy et al. 2019a; Carmenta et al. 2021). The material environment plays a central role in shaping individual and collective identities. For communities that rely on fire for daily activities – such as land clearing, hunting, or maintaining biodiversity – these practices are deeply connected to their sense of place. Just as livelihoods are shaped by resource ecologies, fire use is embedded in the community's ethos. As discussed in the introduction, fire management in rural societies is not merely a practical tool, but a cultural and ecological medium that defines the boundaries of self-determination. Rosales (2022) offers a compelling glimpse into how opposing worldviews can come into conflict over the use of fire. For the Tau-Buhid indigenous community in Mindoro, land is viewed as collective property, defined and maintained through ancestral practices and spiritual customs. Within this worldview, fire is a ritualised tool to mark land use and uphold communal stewardship. In contrast, the state employs fire as a technical instrument for conservation, framing its own ignitions as legal and scientific, while criminalising indigenous burns. The paradox lies in the fact that state-led ignitions, often carried out without firebreaks, have caused damage to Tau-Buhid plots and homes. This tension highlights not only a dispute over fire management, but a deeper struggle over the right to define and care for land. As Rosales writes, “the state's attempt to ‘extinguish fire’ in their lifeworld through combined science and law could only mean loss of land, control of resources therein, loss of autonomy and rights over their frontier, and loss of self-determination, all of which would ultimately lead to ethnocide” (ibid.: 243).

In contexts where anti-fire policies expose broader conflicts related to modes of production and historical land use, an infra-political analysis focuses on fire-mediated narratives of resistance, making the hidden transcripts of marginalised groups more visible. Achieving an insider view requires cultural competence and long-term ethnographic immersion. Not surprisingly, the works referenced in this section are primarily single case studies, grounded in extended research within the studied communities. While this approach limits generalisations, a common thread across these studies is the recognition of indigenous knowledge as crucial for ecosystem preservation and the political control of fire management. Huffman (2013: 1) defines traditional fire knowledge as “fire-related knowledge, beliefs and practices that have been developed and applied on specific landscapes for specific purposes by long-time inhabitants”. There is broad consensus that this knowledge is increasingly sidelined in many regions of the Global South and excluded from current wildfire risk strategies

(Devisscher et al. 2018). These strategies are dominated by a Western scientific perspective that overlooks the “nuances and intentionality” of indigenous methods, often dismissing them as outdated or unscientific (Shaffer 2010). As previously noted, in post-colonial settings, this epistemic dominance echoes colonial policies, persisting in new forms of material exploitation and cultural violence (Rodriguez et al. 2023). This has prompted calls to decolonize Western-centric fire management approaches, even within research communities themselves (Crocker et al. 2024).

Beneath the apparent mismatch between indigenous and non-indigenous knowledge systems (Mistry et al. 2016) lies a web of deeper issues. Although there is growing interest in integrating various forms of environmental knowledge to validate local fire use, the survival of indigenous cultures remains a pressing concern amid modernisation and cultural homogenisation (Rodriguez et al. 2023; Tornorsam et al. 2024). The progressive erosion of traditional knowledge frames environmental governance as a matter of self-determination and cultural reaffirmation. While it is relatively straightforward to position these processes of cultural change within power imbalances, lingering epistemological challenges demand attention. In the first place, labelling knowledge as either “indigenous” or “Western” as shorthand for non-scientific and scientific understandings is problematic, as it hypostatizes binary modes of thought into static and universal categories. According to Agrawal (1995), this is untenable on ontological, epistemological, and methodological grounds, as knowledge can never be fixed in time and space. The dichotomy indigenous/non-indigenous overlooks the existence of multiple, localised knowledge systems, each with its own logic. Furthermore, it reproduces early anthropological misconceptions reinforcing a divide between “primitive” and “modern” cultures.

In relation to fire management, Vazquez et al. (2022) argue that the distinction between traditional and modern practices may be less significant than the practical application of local knowledge to address ecological dynamics. From this viewpoint, a key issue concerns scale: the context-dependent nature of traditional fire knowledge, which is specific to particular ecosystems and fire regimes, complicates its broader application. Moreover, the integration of local knowledge into scientific frameworks raises ethical concerns regarding appropriation and the potential loss of indigenous control over traditional practices (ibid.). While these dilemmas are not the primary focus of this article, they undermine the reflexive governance required for more equitable and inclusive fire management solutions (Rodriguez et al. 2023). Additionally, they influence the conditions under which the hidden transcripts of infra-politics become accessible to external researchers. Addressing these concerns, therefore, necessitates careful consideration of the researcher’s positionality, as engaging with local knowledge involves navigating power dynamics and ethical responsibilities.

Conclusions

In this article, we have presented the current state of the social and political science literature on wildfires in the Global South by introducing a multi-scalar theoretical framework to identify the diverse actors, interests, and power dynamics shaping fire governance. The four levels – *supra-politics*, *state-politics*, *para-politics*, *infra-politics* – are distinguished for analytical purposes only and should not be seen as separate or hierarchically ordered. Rather, their interplay varies across contexts, determined by the specific ecological, social, and political conditions that define fire practices and governance.

We showed that wildfire politics is influenced by global norms and institutions, particularly those stemming from international frameworks on disaster risk reduction and climate change mitigation. These norms inform wildfire narratives and policies across all levels of governance through formal agreements, technical standards, and financial instruments. Although such influences are often perceived as external, they are in fact deeply embedded in national and sub-national fire policy regimes. At the same time, we emphasized that supra-political interventions frequently reflect technocratic rationalities or revive colonial-era conservation ideologies that portray local burning practices as inherently destructive. The resulting anti-fire discourse fuels policy blueprints that tend to marginalize, criminalize, or exclude indigenous and smallholder land-use practices. A widely acknowledged concern in the literature is that global fire governance often reproduces forms of epistemic violence by privileging scientific and expert knowledge while sidelining local epistemologies and traditional ecological knowledge systems.

While the influence of global-scale dynamics on local fire policy regimes has grown significantly in recent decades, largely driven by international aid, fire itself has a much longer history as a tool of territorial control and land appropriation. During European colonial expansion, it was strategically deployed to displace indigenous populations, reshape landscapes, and impose new systems of property and governance. This legacy continues in many post-colonial contexts, where fire regulation reinforces state authority and development agendas. More broadly, state control over fire operates on both symbolic and material levels. State policies often frame fire through technocratic and bureaucratic paradigms, excluding local knowledge systems and concealing the socio-political inequalities tied to land use. Forestry bureaucracies, in particular, have historically served as instruments of dispossession, legitimizing elite and commercial claims to land under the banners of conservation or development. A growing body of scholarship highlight how the racialization and criminalization of fire use by indigenous groups and local communities legitimizes top-down governance, while deflecting scrutiny from the role of state and corporate actors in environmental degradation. The prevailing emergency discourse surrounding wildfires further amplifies this dynamic, hardening regulatory approaches and marginalizing community participation.

Our broader argument, however, is that wildfire politics cannot be fully understood through a state-centred framework alone. Beneath the surface of international initiatives and state regulations lies a dense and often overlooked grey area. This includes a diverse array of actors and processes – from extra-legal forms of sovereignty to subaltern resistance – that contribute to the creation of fire-prone landscapes. In many rural contexts, the presence (or absence) of landscape fires reflects the coalescence of state and corporate interests through patronage networks, particularly in the agribusiness sector. Fire, in this sense, is part and parcel of the political economy of resource extraction, and the way it is regulated (or left unregulated) illuminates persistent patterns of dispossession and resource control. On the other hand, fire can also become a tool of political agency for marginalized groups, especially when subsistence burning is criminalized or suppressed. From this perspective, the relationship between state and non-state actors is rarely straightforward. Authorities often navigate the tension between formal state mandates and local realities, which may involve informal arrangements or strategic silences to meet community needs. In contrast, the informality of state involvement in some cases enables corporate exploitation and environmental degradation, as local state agents may covertly support corporate interests, facilitating illegal practices like logging or

land clearing. Ultimately, these dynamics highlight the importance of recognizing a wide spectrum of power relations at play, far beyond the official state apparatus.

In our experience across Latin America, Southern Africa, and Southeast Asia (Author et al. 2023a, Author et al. 2023b, Author et al. 2024, Author et al. 2025), we have observed the sensitivities involved in conducting empirical research on these dynamics, which we address here under the headings of *para-* and *infra-politics*. Even when the flames are in plain sight, the thick haze of vested interests makes open, public discussion nearly impossible. In countries characterized by patrimonial logics and undemocratic governments (or nominally democratic ones with insufficient protection of fundamental rights), fire is quite often expression of power asymmetries that cannot be exposed without endangering one's personal safety. As outsiders from the Global North, we have had the privilege of addressing open secrets with a breadth and ease that local researchers are denied, forcing them to either dilute or omit the political substratum of their work. This not only underscores the intense politicization of fire but also helps explain the relatively small number of studies that explore these issues. Most importantly, it presents an ethical dilemma concerning the impact of research on a subject burdened by deep vulnerabilities and inequalities. This dilemma remains ongoing but should prompt the academic community engaged in fire research to reflect on how to overcome barriers that perpetuate oppressive structures and eventually blur the understanding of the phenomenon. We believe this is a crucial aspect by which we can measure not only the genuine decolonization of knowledge systems but also our professional and moral responsibility towards the impact of research, which should be grounded in an ethics of care.

This brings us to a final point we feel is crucial to highlight. The need for greater ethical awareness regarding the multifaceted nature of wildfire politics is driven by the tangible consequences it has on the lives of people living in fire-prone landscapes. The mainstream disaster-oriented narrative on wildfires, discussed in the introduction, has profound and far-reaching implications for policy: with respect to the direction of programs and funding lines established in international forums, particularly at the UN level; on the institutional actors and/or civil society organizations tasked with taking operational responsibility for fire management (and therefore the expertise and knowledge they embody); and on the development of legislation and regulations at the national and sub-national levels. The implementation of all these elements is directly influenced by the overarching narrative through which we conceptualize wildfires. The concrete risk, therefore, is the perpetuation of grossly misguided perspectives that overlook the ecological characteristics of local ecosystems and the livelihoods of those who depend on them. The well-documented failure of the suppression paradigm in much of the Global North should serve as a lesson in this regard. In the Global South, an additional dimension exacerbates the problem: the colonial legacy – sometimes embedded in legislation and management approaches inherited from colonial administrations and never critically examined, sometimes reinforced by the supranational agenda itself when blueprints are applied across the board, without prior understanding of local fire behaviour or the socio-economic fabric of a given area. All this underscores how *politics*, in the broad sense of the term, determines the conditions of fire activity, not the other way around. And it highlights the need for conceptual innovation in scientific approaches to overcome the siloed thinking that has long hindered fire research. Developing a critical understanding of these interconnections and their policy implications is essential for learning how to manage the complexity of the socio-environmental metabolic relations mediated by fire.

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